

Psychological Conditions for Correction and Optimization of Personal Development of Adolescents with Depressive Disorders

Nelia BIHUN¹,
Olena MALYNA²,
Maksym DOICHYK³,
Ihor HOIAN⁴,
Nina HARKAVENKO⁵,
Svitlana SYMONENKO⁶

¹National Pedagogical Dragomanov University, Ukraine, nelabigun@gmail.com

²Zaporizhzhia National University, Ukraine, lenamalina1975@gmail.com

³Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, Ukraine, maksimdoichyk@ukr.net

⁴Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, Ukraine, ivigoian@gmail.com

⁵Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine, n.harkavenko@chnu.edu.ua

⁶South Ukrainian National Pedagogical University named after K.D.Ushynsky, Ukraine, si38mon@ukr.net

Abstract: *The article presents a theoretical generalization and a new solution to a scientific problem, expressed in the application of an innovative personal approach to solving the problem of adolescent depressive disorders, the basis of which is the scientific and methodological interpretation of personal development as a defining construct of the system of psychological conditions for the onset of depressive disorders, models of their diagnosis and psychological conditions for overcoming, which ensures the formation of adolescents' ability to effective personal self-regulation and an arbitrary choice of constructive ways of self-realization. The methodological foundations of the study of the personal properties of adolescents with depressive disorders are disclosed, a program for the diagnosis of personal symptoms of depressive disorders of various forms of severity in adolescent schoolchildren is presented; carried out a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the results of the ascertaining experiment on the psychological conditions of the onset of depressive disorders in adolescent schoolchildren and the personality traits of adolescents with depressive disorders; the description of personal phenomenology and symptomatology of depressive disorders in adolescents has been carried out. Theoretical substantiation of the formative experiment is given, the program of correction and optimization of personal development of teenagers as a means of overcoming their depressive disorders is presented, the quantitative and qualitative analysis of the results of its approbation is carried out. A profound restructuring of the structure and qualitative characteristics of the psychological conditions of the personal development of adolescents, their system of personal self-regulation, optimizes the functioning of the mechanism of personal sensitivity - "Ego" -tolerance to destructive influences, is, as the results of the application of the experimental correctional and developmental program, an effective way to overcome depression in adolescents' disorders.*

Keywords: *personality development interpretation, personal self-regulation, constructive self-realisation ways, diagnostics of personal symptoms, adolescent secondary school students, correction program.*

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Introduction

The modern trends to the education reform are centralised in the idea to develop and implement the latest psychological and pedagogical techniques that are primarily oriented to the development of the school student's personality. Ensuring the conditions for an independent, harmonious, active personality to grow, to be able to creatively program his or her life and to individually realise his or her full potential, the Ukrainian scientists determine the tasks of the contemporary general education school as prioritised (Behas et al., 2019; Bekh, 1998; Bezliudnyi et al., 2019; Bulakh, 2003; Nerubasska & Maksymchuk 2020; Nerubasska et al., 2020; Palamarchuk et al., 2020; Sitovskyi et al., 2019). In the system of these conditions, the psychological conditions have a special place, as they directly serve as general mechanisms of the human being's personality development and mechanisms of his/her development in some specific crisis states, particularly in the situations of appearing and progressing depressive disorders. Prevention of neuropsychiatric disorders, providing conditions for maintaining the mental health of children and young students occupies a special place in the system of current issues of modern domestic school. According to statistics, the number of schoolchildren with mental and behavioral disorders has increased by 16.7% over the last decade. The danger of depressive disorders both in adults and adolescents is first and foremost associated with a higher suicidal risk: depression takes the second place (17,3%) among the reasons of suicidal deaths. Smulevych (2015) indicates that suicidal thoughts and attempts are registered in 61.9% young people and teenagers with depressive disorders.

The justification of the relevance of studying the problem of depressive disorders in adolescents requires that its age-related aspect should be taken into consideration, in particular, the analysis of adverse effects of the origin and progression of depression namely at the age of adolescence when dramatic changes happen in the structure of the personality of a young human being. Immaturity of the adolescents' personality causes their vulnerability to the destructive influence of depression by provoking the hazard of a depressive deformation of the mindfulness development processes, formation of personality new traits, social adaptation and integration. Futhermore, the risk of formation of premorbid traits of the personality as one of the psychological conditions for dysthymic disorders and chronic depressions to occur at a juvenile and mature age increases in the midst of adolescent depressive disorders.

Thus, in the context of the analysis of the problem of adolescent depression, it becomes necessary to study the psychological conditions of the personal development of adolescents with depressive disorders, in particular, the identification of depressogenic internally personal and externally personal conditions for the development of depression, as well as modeling the psychological conditions for the correction and optimization of the personal development of adolescents as a means of preventing and overcoming it.

However, it should be pointed out that the research of adolescent's depressions is mostly performed in terms of the psychomedical and psychotherapeutic approaches. The underdevelopment of the problem in the realm of psychological science and practice causes that insufficient consideration of the specifics of teen depressions, i.a. in their genesis of such fundamental psychological conditions as domination in the structure of the teenager's personality development, crisis of an individual's personality development at a teen age; personal symptoms and signs are underused in revealing depressive disorders; a limited arsenal of special programs and methods of assistance for adolescents with depressive disorders which are available for psychologists at educational institutions. The social significance of the problem and its incomplete study made us choose such a subject of our research.

Objective: to theoretically prove the psychological conditions of the personality development of adolescents with depressive disorders, to assess their personal traits empirically, to elaborate and to test correction methods for treating depression in secondary school students at a teen age.

Review of Literature

Depression has been known to mankind since ancient times. The first traces to study the nature of depression are found in the works of the Ancient Greek philosophers (Hippocrates, 1936; Aristotle, 2000), who called this disorder as melancholy. The term "depression" was recognised in the medical science in the second half of XIX century when the science began studying this affective disorder.

Over a long period of study of depressive disorders, scientists have proposed a large number of hypotheses and theories designed to explain the causes of depression. Generally, they present two approaches to the study of depressive disorders: psychiatric-biological and psychological-sociological. The representatives of the first school (Asberg et al., 1976; Davis, 1970) accentuate the role of biological factors of appearing depressive disorders;

the advocates of the second school (Ellis, 1999; Freud, 1968; Horney, 1997) substantiate the ideas of their advanced psychological and sociocultural nature.

The recognised conceptual position is such one, according to which biological, psychological and social factors interact and have a complex impact on a human being (biopsychosocial approach by Engel, 1962; integrative approach by Hell, 1999). It is believed that the initial factors are biological (original disposition to depression, physiological and hormonal changes in the organism, lasting and severe somatic diseases etc.). Psychological factors form on their basis (fear of loss, psychological dependence on parents, self-distrust, narcissist vulnerability, mental fatigue and burnout etc.). Social factors (deformations of the educational influence, family discords, death of close people, conflict peer relationships, political and socio-economic instability in the country) serve as stimuli that actualise the effect of biological and psychological reasons of depression.

The model of psychological conditions of progression of depressive disorders, which is the first in the global science, is a model of the origin of melancholy (Hippocrates-Galenus), the fundamentals of which consist in the aggregation of specific personality traits forming on the basis of the melancholic temper and uniting in such personality traits as propensity for sadness and psychological vulnerability. The mentioned model provided a basis for the personal approach particularly evident as initiation of the scientific tradition to interpret depression as personal issue and personal determined phenomenon.

The most important psychological conditions among the personal determinants of depressive disorders discovered in the studies are: personality conflicts (Freud, 1968; Horney, 1997), specific personality traits (sensitivity, emotional lability, high anxiety, low self-esteem, self-distrust, modesty, sensitivity to opinions and estimating viewpoints of surrounding people, socio-psychological dependence, asthenic constitution and so forth), depressogenic personal traits of parents (personality weakness, personality constriction, personality closeness, personality proneness to conflict); psychological conditions of the strict family education with the child's ego suppression.

The analysis of the results of the research of depressive disorders attests that the sphere, which is ineluctably affected notwithstanding the specifics of the origin and progression of depressive disorders, is namely the personality self-regulation system. The proportion of personal factors in the depressogenesis is so high that defining depression as personality disorder does not look like exaggeration.

From our point of view, depression is depersonalisation (ego disorders, issues with the personality self-regulatory functioning) dependent on tendencies, loss of life productivity causing the deployment of internal and external destructive processes in an individual's life activities and related thereto emotional tolls and involutions.

The beginning of the studies of depressions in children and teenagers started approximately in the first half of XX century (Bowlby, 1961; Spitz, 1945). The problem of teen depressive disorders remains to be a subject of studies of the contemporary researchers (Antropov, 2001). The studies are carried out in various aspects: detection of reasons, determination of symptoms and signs, description of different forms of depression, elaboration of methods and ways of its treatment, amelioration.

According to the research outcomes, depressive disorders in children and teenagers are specific and differ in particular aspects from similar states in adults (for instance, propensity for particular forms of depression, age-related peculiarities of factors of the origin of depressive disorders, polymorphism and atypicality of their signs).

Basing on the theoretical-methodological analysis of the scientific studies of the problem of teen depressions, we designed a model of psychological conditions of the personality development of teenagers suffering depressive disorders. This model represents a structure of macro- and micro-levels of psychological conditions that can be interpreted, with reference to the depression core, as external personal and internal personal conditions.

The macro-level of depressogenic psychological conditions of the individual's personality development at a teen age comprises: present teen dichotomy (dichotomy "childhood-adulthood"), situations of the personal choice of an external and internal orientation in the attitude of adequacy; natural organic aptitude and readiness for sensitivity and influence, as a product of the specifics of the higher nervous system and temper; imbalance of the constructive and dominating destructive orientations in the system of personality self-regulation; psychological conditions of crisis life situations as a result of the effect from the aggregation of destructive influences and their continuous presence in the form of potential threats.

No self-sufficiency or its low level creates a core of the macro-level of depressogenic psychological conditions, where the main ones are: deformations and imbalance of the personality self-regulatory system – low or blocked productivity of the self-attitude function, self-defence, self-expression, self-control, self-realisation (self-depreciation, non-valid tendencies in feelings about yourself; imbalance of the self-defence and self-

expression functions); deformations of the subsystem of personal relevance and personal sensitivity – producing exaggerated patterns of influence and their personal value, protective expectations regarding destructive influences; transformations of the personal significance of influence into the destructive, psychologic production of a virtual depressive environment; low “Self”-tolerance to destructive influences as integral form of internal personal preconditions and conditions for the progression of depressive disorders.

The model of psychological conditions of the progression of depression in teenagers elaborated on grounds of the theoretical generalisation justifies the conclusion that the approach adequate to the problem of treatment of teen depressive disorders is a personal approach, the fundamentals of which consist in the research and methodological interpretation of the personality development as determinative construct of the system of psychological conditions of the origin of depressive disorders, their diagnostic models and treatment, which provide an opportunity for developing the ability of teenagers to the productive personal self-regulation and optional choice of constructive ways of self-realisation.

Materials & Methods

For determining the peculiarities of the origin and progression of depression at an adolescent age and personality traits of teenagers with depressive disorders, the following diagnostic methods are used: Beck’s depression scale (1974, cited in Davis, 1980), Zhmurov’s technique of differential diagnostics of depressive states (2002) adapted by us for adolescence; self-esteem scale; technique for studying the level of aspiration, as modified by Kurek (1997), anxiety scale (Gelikon, 1995), inventory of Eysenck (1999), pathocharacterological diagnostic questionnaire of Lichko (1999), Kettel’s personal 16-PF-questionnaire (Akhmedzhanov, 1996).

The experimental sample made 392 secondary school students aged 11 to 16.

One of the main tasks of the research was to experimentally assess the influence of psychological conditions of the personality development of teenagers on the origin and progression of their depressive disorders. For the experimental proof of the determinant bounds and bondages detected by the method of theoretical modelling, one selected the indices of the personality development of teenagers, which could be detected with the help of the reliable standardised techniques, and which could concurrently represent depressogenic psychological conditions. These indices included the phenomena of self-esteem, levels of aspiration, anxiety, temper,

accentuations of personality traits, personality properties, and productivity in different spheres of life.

The worked-out program of correctional-developmental work with teenagers suffering depressive disorders is oriented at renewing and developing their personal self-regulatory system, mainly such its functions as self-treatment, self-protection, self-expression, self-control and self-realisation. The optimisation of the said basic functions of the personal self-regulatory system produces a wholistic effect of the rise and evolution of some constructive tendencies including the following for removing depressive disorders:

- tendency for curing teen dichotomy (enhanced inner orientation of the adequacy feeling, increasing level of independence, self-sufficiency, self-regulation, lower social dependence and conformity);
- lower level of the personal sensitivity (lower propensity for exaggeration of the personal significance of destructive influences, lower level of anxiety, uncontrollableness of fears, tension, vulnerability, emotional instability, bashfulness, self-distrust);
- tendency to enhance the positive self-attitude (higher self-esteem, lower inferiority complex, coping with despair from an own ego);
- tendency to increase “Self”-tolerance to destructive influences (increased level of self-control, independence, self-consistency, emotional balance, emotional resilience, confidence, overcoming constraint, increased level of self-protection and self-expression, overcoming the suppressed ego);
- tendency to renew the vital productivity (returning the feeling of perspective of an own existence, feeling of success and satisfaction in the main life spheres of a teenager);
- tendency of lowering and disappearing of personal and external symptoms of depressive disorders.

Thus, the treatment of teen depressive disorders was carried out through the deep restructuring and reform of the qualitative properties of psychological conditions of the personality development of teenagers by optimising their self-regulatory systematic functions.

In order to approbate our designed program for prevention and treatment of depressive disorders in adolescents, an experimental and control group was formed. The experimental group included 16 secondary school students with a light form of depression, 16 with a moderate one; the control group included 17 subjects in a state of light depression, 15 – moderate depression.

Results & Discussion

The analysis of the research results shows that almost a half of the teenagers examined (42.09%) suffers different forms of depressive disorders. We note that 28.06% subjects have light depression, 12.50% teenagers are in a state of moderate depression, and 2.04% secondary school students are diagnosed with severe depression.

The numerical relation of boys and girls suffering depressive disorders is 1:2.

The research results make it possible to state that the period of the highest risk of appearing depression is 13-14 years of age: most of adolescents (69.09%) suffering depression are secondary school students who go through the so called “crisis of 13 years”. Deep qualitative changes of the mental growth process go right at this age phase and cause a teenager’s high responsiveness, vulnerability and sensitivity, his defencelessness to slings and arrows of life.

The results of studying the indices of the personality development of teenagers with depressive disorders are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. *Indices of the Relation of Personality Traits of Teenagers and Depressive Disorders*
n = 165

Parameters Studied	Forms of Depression					
	Light		Medium		High	
	%	rx _y	%	rx _y	%	Rx _y
<i>Self-Esteem</i>						
Inadequate, inflated	-	-	-	-	-	-
Adequate with an uprising trend	1.82	0.42	-	-	-	-
Adequate	64.54	0.81*	36.17	- 0.52	12.50	-
Adequate with a downward trend	21.82	0.52	34.04	0.94*	25.00	0.95*
Inadequate, low	11.82	0.50	29.79	0.89*	62.50	0.99*
<i>Level of Aspiration</i>						
High	18.19	0.42	-	-	-	-
Medium	44.54	0.88*	38.30	0.38	25.00	- 0.44
Low	37.27	0.53	61.70	0.97*	75.00	0.99*
<i>Anxiety</i>						
High	48.18	- 0.37	53.19	0.96*	62.50	0.98*
Medium	51.82	0.69*	46.81	0.45	37.50	0.38
Low	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Temper</i>						
Melancholic	33.64	- 0.39	57.44	0.98*	62.50	0.99*

Choleric	36.36	0.49	27.66	0.50	25.00	0.50
Sanguineous	28.19	0.97*	14.90	- 0.86*	12.50	-
Phlegmatic (lymphatic)	1.81	0.99*	-	-	-	-

- Notes: 1. r_{xy} – value of Pirson`s correlation ratio
2. Strong correlation if $r_{xy} > 0.6$

Relying on the experimental data, the psychological traits of adolescents suffering depressive disorders were determined. Most of them are secondary school students with low self-esteem, high anxiety, melancholic or choleric temper, accentuated traits according to the psychastenic, sensitive, asthenoneurotic or cycloid type (14.90% secondary school students in a state of moderate depression had an asthenoneurotic type of the accentuated temper; 17.02% - a sensitive type; 19.15% - a psychastenic type; 23.40% - a cycloid type; the group of test subjects comprised 25.00% with a psychastenic type of the accentuated temper, 25.00% with a mixed type of the accentuated temper, 12.50% with a cycloid type of the accentuated temper, 12.50% with an asthenoneurotic type of the accentuated temper). There is a two-sided concatenation of depression and the level of aspiration, self-esteem and anxiety of teenagers. Low self-esteem, marked anxiety and an outstanding level of aspiration cause depressive disorders. Concurrently, depression cause lower self-esteem, aspiration level and higher anxiety.

Absent personal traits detected in teenagers with depressive disorders in the structure of the personality of adolescents justify a generalisation being fundamental for the research: depression – a phenomenon of the personality sphere, problem of the teenager`s personality development in general, personality self-regulatory mechanisms in particular.

The processing of the results received by the procedure of control testing gave a comprehensive sense of those changes happened in the personality and psychoemotional spheres of the both groups studied during the experiment, an opportunity to assess the efficiency and strength of the designed program for treatment of depressive disorders of teenagers (Table 2).

Table 2. Results of the Examination of Test Persons in the Experimental (EG) and Control (CG) Groups According to the Method of Diagnostics of Depressive States $n = 64$

Forms of Depression	Number of Test Persons in %				
	Examination 1	Examination 2	Examination 3	Examination 4	Examination 5

	EG	CG								
Absent	–	–	18.75	3.13	31.25	–	75.00	–	87.50	–
Light	50.00	53.13	43.75	50.00	56.25	50.00	25.00	50.00	12.50	46.875
Medium	50.00	46.87	37.50	46.87	12.50	50.00	–	46.87	–	46.875
High	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	3.13	–	6.25

The figures provided in Table 2 show the positive dynamics of the psychoemotional state of the test persons in the experimental group. In particular, 18.75% teenagers had no depressive disorders in two months after the beginning of the psychocorrectional process. According to the results of the last control diagnostic examination, the portion of teenagers without depression made 87.50%.

Summing up the results of the diagnostics of depressive states of the experimental group, we noticed a shift in the quantitative ratio of teenagers with different forms of depression at each experiment stage (see Fig.1).

Fig.1. Dynamics of the ratio of test persons (experimental group) with different forms of depression in the forming experiment

The analysis of the dynamics of the psychoemotional state of test persons in the control group shows a negative trend as reducing number of teenagers with light depression (from 53.13% to 46.87%) and moderate depression turning into the severe one that was noted in 6.25% of the teenagers. It should be pointed out that a worse psychoemotional state of secondary school students in the control group was registered mainly in the period of completion of the school term or year. It provides insight that the intensiveness of depressogenic factors as higher school load, higher requirements and summative assessment increases towards the end of the

study year. Hence, the number of stressful situations stimulating depressive reactions in emotionally sensitive teenagers increases too.

The statistical analysis of the experimental material according to Student's t-test showed the veracity of differences of the indices of depressive disorders between the first and second diagnostic check-ups: $t = 2.96$ and statistically significant when $\rho \leq 0.01$ in the experimental group and statistically insignificant in the control group, where $t = -1.57$ when $\rho \leq 0.05$.

To verify the hypothesis provided and to determine whether it is true that positive changes in the psychological state of the teenagers with depression are a consequence of an increased level of development of their personality functions, we studied the dynamics of personal changes in test persons in the control and experimental groups during the forming experiment. For this purpose, we used Kettel's personal 16-PF-questionnaire (Akhmedzhanov, 1996) (Table 3).

Table 3. Results of the Examination of Test Persons in the Experimental (EG) and Control (CG) Groups According to Kettel's Personal 16-PF-Questionnaire (Akhmedzhanov, 1996)
 $n = 64$

Factor	Number of Test Persons in %											
	Examination 1						Examination 2					
	EG	CG	EG	CG	EG	CG	EG	CG	EG	CG	EG	CG
C	-	-	37.50	34.375	62.50	65.625	15.625	-	62.50	34.375	21.875	65.625
E	-	-	43.75	46.875	56.25	53.125	3.13	-	62.50	46.875	34.37	53.125
G	40.625	34.375	37.50	40.625	21.875	25.00	46.875	34.375	37.50	40.625	15.625	25.00
H	-	-	50.00	43.75	50.00	56.25	18.75	-	68.75	43.75	12.50	56.25
O	75.00	78.125	25.00	21.875	-	-	15.625	75.00	65.625	25.00	18.75	-
Q3	15.625	21.875	37.50	43.75	46.875	34.375	28.125	21.875	46.875	43.75	25.00	34.375
Q4	46.875	50.00	53.125	50.00	-	-	18.75	50.00	81.25	50.00	-	-
MD	6.25	6.25	31.25	28.125	62.50	65.625	25.00	6.25	53.125	28.125	21.875	65.625
Factors Assessment	High		Average		Low		High		Average		Low	

The results of the analysis of the experimental data obtained in the summative and control assessments show the positive dynamics in the personality sphere of test persons from the experimental group. Some significant changes in the indices of expressiveness of the factors C – “emotional instability – emotional stability”, H – “bashfulness – boldness”, O – “assertiveness – bashfulness”, Q4 – “slackness – tension”, MD – “self-esteem adequacy” and others (see Table 3). There is no positive dynamics of the personality development detected while examining test persons of the control group.

The comparative analysis of the diagnostic data obtained according to Kettel's personal 16-PF-questionnaire (Akhmedzhanov, 1996) shows that the carried out the psychocorrective work stimulated the positive personality changes in test persons of the experimental group manifesting in a strengthened emotional stability and development of self-regulation of emotions of teenagers; a lower level of anxiety, exaltation, weakening depressiveness and inner tension; developing skills of self-control of behaviour; an increased feeling of self-confidence and refocusing from the search of support and reliance in the group to self-reliance; weakening bashfulness, constraint and adequate increase of self-esteem.

Thus, the results of the forming experiment confirm the efficiency of a designed model of psychological conditions of correction and optimisation of the personality development of teenagers with depressive disorders (the model is schematically presented in Fig.2).

In designing the model described above, we were motivated by the methodological insight about the productivity of the model construction method consisting in finding key solutions of research challenges. By applying to the problem of adolescent depressive disorders, it manifested in discovering means of a proposed model of ways to research psychological factors and mechanisms of development of depressive disorders of teenagers, discovery of their symptoms and signs and ways of treatment.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the results obtained consist in the following: *firstly*, the scientific-theoretical justification of the systematic nature of determination, through psychological conditions, of the processes of origin, progression and treatment of depressive disorders in teenagers. The structure of psychological conditions of the personality development serving as mechanisms of origin of depressive disorders (psychological conditions of teen dichotomy, natural-organic influence-dependence, external orientation of the conformity attitude, deformation of the personal self-regulatory functions, high personal sensitivity, low "Self"-tolerance to destructive influences, suppressed "ego") as well as the structure of psychological conditions of correction and optimisation of readiness to the personality self-regulation, creation and development of the trend of treatment of teen dichotomy, lowering of the personal sensitivity level and influence-dependence, progression of the positive self-attitude, increase of "Self"-tolerance to destructive influences, life productivity optimisation were determined. The author *enhanced and extended* the phenomenology and symptomatology of depressive disorders of various manifestation forms by describing personal features of their manifestation at an adolescent age, designed a model of

correction and optimisation of the personality development of teenagers as psychological basis for treating their depressive disorders.

Fig.2. Psychological conditions of correction and optimisation of the personality development of teenagers with depressive disorders

The scientific representation of the phenomenon of depressive disorders, role of the personality development factors in their genesis, progression and amelioration, information of psychological means to handle depressive disorders at an adolescent age are *further elaborated*.

The practical importance of the obtained results consists in the designed and approved program for detection of personal symptoms and signs of different depressive disorders in secondary school students-teenagers, psychocorrection program for treatment of depressive disorders in teenagers. On grounds of the research results, the author elaborated the practical recommendations, which can be used by school psychologists, counsellors, rehabilitation therapists, teachers, parents for developing the personality of depressed teenagers, preventing and treating their personality-depressive disorders. The obtained data about psychological conditions of origin and treatment of depressive disorders in school students-teenagers can be used for improving the content and management of comprehensive school institutions, for extending (specifying, enriching) the content of educational-professional training programs for psychologists at higher educational institutions, academic levels "Bachelor", "Specialist", "Master", particularly in teaching such subjects as "Clinical Psychology", "Psychopathology", "Psychocorrection", "Psychological Counselling".

Conclusions

This article provides the theoretical generalisation and new solution of the scientific problem manifested in applying an innovative personal approach to the resolution of the problem of adolescent depressive disorders, the fundamentals of which consist in the research and methodological approach as determinative construct of the system of psychological conditions of origin of depressive disorders, their diagnostic models and psychological conditions of their amelioration providing for a forming propensity of teenagers for efficient personal self-regulation and optional choice of constructive ways of self-realisation.

The approaches formed in studying adult depressions prevail in the studies of adolescent depressions. It results in such consequences: the specifics of teen depressions is deficiently considered; there is a rote transfer of the methods of diagnostics and treatment of teen depressions that results in disregarding such fundamental psychological conditions of the process of development of teenagers as the personality development dominating in its structure, teen age sensitivity to the individual's personality development, depressogenic nature of the teenager crisis; personal symptoms of depressive disorders are incompletely used; the arsenal of programs and methods of

psychological aid to teenagers extends slowly; there is no special approach created for solving the problem of adolescent depressive disorders.

Resolving the problem of teen depressive disorders is an important component of the movement for constructivism, implementation of the humanistic principle of fighting for life and mature self-realisation of every person. The following was ascertained in the research:

- adolescent depressive disorders are noted for their high destructive potential and consequently constitute a menace to an individual's life at an adolescent age and at further stages of existence: depressive issues, which were not shed in the period of their appearance, turn into the chronic ones and transform into the system of depressogenic personality traits – a so called depressive personality that becomes an inner source of life threats. The range of such threats is wide: from deformation of personality functions, for instance, disorder of the function of positive self-attitude and related anguish of mind to the phenomenon of “broken life” and even its physical destruction as suicide;

- the nature of adolescent depressive disorders poses the necessity of forming professional-ethical imperative predominantly addressed to the psychological science and practice, the content of which uncovers itself in such requirements: to adhere to the enhanced concept of the group of risk of appearing depressive disorders by using the personal approach symptomatology therefor; not to leave the problem of a detected depressive disorder unsolved; to provide teenagers with depressive disorders with urgent systematic psychological aid.

Psychological conditions of the personality development and depressive disorders have a staged dependence level, the nature of which is reflected by the formula “The more destructive influence of psychological conditions of the personality development, the more advanced depressive disorders: the more advanced depressive disorders, the more destructive respective psychological conditions of the personality development.” This common pattern, as we can note in the correlation analysis data, is manifested in the relations of components of these phenomena: the lower self-esteem, the more advanced depressive disorder and the higher anxiety level; the lower personality adaptive potential, the more severe depressive disorder; the more severe depressive disorder, the lower adaptive potential of personality traits. Determining these and other dependences has become a key conclusion of the research that makes it possible to detect advanced inner symptoms and signs of depression, as opposed to the traditional methods of diagnostics of adolescent depressions, its phenomenological core providing for an opportunity of not only qualitative diagnostics of

depressive disorders in their formed full-blown state, but anticipation of their origin and early detection.

The psychological condition serving as a central regulator of the personal self-regulatory system as a functional core of the personality development is personal sensitivity – functional characteristics of the personal self-regulatory system defining the level of “Ego”-tolerance, which is a mechanism of stabilisation, integrity and self-sufficiency of an individual’s personality functioning in the situation of perception and influence.

According to the data obtained in the experimental research, interpersonal psychological conditions that determine high personal anxiety; unstable self-esteem with a downward trend; a non-uniform level of aspiration tending to be inadequately outsized or downgraded; components of personal lack of balance in the structure of the melancholic and choleric types of temper; accentuation according to the psychastenic, sensitive, asthenoneurotic, cycloid, labile types of temper. Sensitivity, “Ego”-tolerance and depressive disorder have regular dependence of the two types – unilateral dependence: the higher degree of personal sensitivity, the lower “Ego”-tolerance to destructive influences, the higher probability of an appearing depressive disorder; and bilateral dependence – the higher degree of personal sensitivity, the lower “Ego”-tolerance to destructive influences, the more severe depressive disorder; the more severe depressive disorder, the higher degree of personal sensitivity and the lower “Self”-tolerance to destructive influences.

The in-depth reforming of the structure and qualitative properties of psychological conditions of the teenagers` personality development, their system of personal self-regulation optimising the personal sensitivity mechanism – “Self”-tolerance to destructive influences is, as evidenced by the results of the applied experimental correction-development program, a productive way to remove depressive disorders of teenagers. The application of the valid reliable standardised techniques and advanced observation attest the accuracy of the data of the teenagers` personality development in the experimental group, positive adaptive changes in the functions of the self-regulatory system: the more positive adaptive changes of the functions of self-attitude, self-defence, self-expression, self-control, self-realisation, the lower degree of symptoms of depressive disorders.

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